

EFFECT OF INCUBATOR POWER SOURCE AND EGG WEIGHT ON HATCHABILITY OF BROILER BREEDER EGGS

Jesuyon O. M. A. * and Akinyemi M. B.

Department of Animal Production and Health, Faculty of Agriculture, Federal University,

P. M. B. 373 Oye-Ekiti, Oye-Omuo Ekiti Highway, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

*Correspondence Author: dr.oluwatosinjesuyon14@gmail.com;
Mobile: +234 806-431-0337; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0901-3556>

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.70118/ajaas.0202505030.21>

ABSTRACT

Many rural and semi-urban areas are not connected to the national electricity grid, thus hampering power-based agricultural activities. The aim was to find a stable alternative to the erratic power supply and high maintenance cost of generating plants for rapid agricultural development in tropical countries. Three hundred and eighty-eight (388) Arbor acre breeder eggs were hatched for chicks, to compare the effect of incubator power-source and egg weight on hatching traits. The CRD in a 2×2 factorial treatment - power source by egg weight - was employed. Records collected were number of eggs set, fertile eggs set, hatchability on eggs set, hatchability on fertile eggs, viable

chicks on fertile eggs, dead in shell on fertile eggs and reject chicks on fertile eggs. These were analysed with SAS version 8 (2008) software, using General Linear Model for the analysis of variance and Duncan Multiple Range Test ($\alpha=0.05$) for mean separation. Medium-sized eggs by

solar-

powered incubator produced the highest hatchability of eggs set (HES), hatchability of fertile eggs (FES) and least dead-in-shell chicks on fertile eggs (DSE) set (73.6, 91.7 and 8.15, %, $p < 0.05$).

Solar powered incubator independently improved HES, FES, and reduced DSE set (72.4, 87.5 and 12.3, %, $p < 0.05$) than the National electricity grid powered incubator ($p < 0.05$) of Arbor acre

~~breeder eggs. The higher hatchability, fertility, and development of viable chicks could be due to its better stability, and this could impact hatchery business and efficiency greatly in terms of turn-~~

INTRODUCTION

profitability and rural poultry development. A constant, stable and cheap energy source to power commercial incubator is required for rapid rural-urban poultry development. The commercial poultry industry depends on day-old chicks hatched from fertile eggs in hatcheries. Egg incubator is a machine that enables poultry breeders to produce more chicks without the mother hen (Iyen & Wunuken, 2024). The quantity and quality of chicks produced depend on the breeder farms and the hatcheries (Yeboea et

al., 2019). A trait of major economic importance in poultry production is hatchability (Khalid et al., 2015). According to King'ori, (2011), breeder factors which affect hatchability include: genetic makeup of the embryo, strain of the birds, health, nutrition and feeding, age of the flock, egg size, egg weight, egg quality, egg storage duration and conditions under which the eggs are stored. Mauldin (2002) reported that hatchery conditions such as temperature, turning, humidity and

ventilation in the incubator, sanitation and hatchability. Ewonetu (2017) reported that egg weight and chick weight at hatching are positively related. Duman *et al.* (2019) have reported that egg weight did not significantly ($p > 0.05$) influence hatchability. Energy is the heartbeat of the poultry egg-hatching industry to power equipment and gadgets. The challenge of power and energy sources for poultry hatcheries is a good pressure on the industry. Most hatchery operations are fossil fuel, and the occasional interruption in power supply to the incubator can greatly affect hatchability and cause major economic loss. The condition of day-old chicks is greatly affected by incubation conditions, timing of hatching, temperature and humidity, and chick handling post-hatch (Beigou *et al.*, 2013). As a result, national grid hydro-electricity, in most cases, is not reliable (Oladapo, 2023), while the initial cost of alternative energy sources - generator, solar system, wind, geothermal, biomass and ocean energy - could be high (Adesina *et al.*, 2024). Fossil fuel which is the commonest source of energy is able to stabilize unpredictable supply and availability. The cost of generator and maintenance are high, and would add to the myriads of challenges in the industry.

The prevailing situation contributes to the high cost of day-old chicks and the collapse of many hatcheries (Osanyinpeju *et al.*, 2018) in recent times. Electric incubators are efficient, and cheaper to manage when run on the National grid electricity; but a high proportion of the population in developing nations is not connected to

national electricity grid (UNEP, 2010). Published statistics show that about 40% of Nigerians have reported that national grid electricity (Plumh, 2019) hinders the poultry hatchery industry to power equipment and gadgets. The challenge of power and energy sources for poultry hatcheries is a good pressure on the industry. Most hatchery operations are fossil fuel, and the occasional interruption in power supply to the incubator can greatly affect hatchability and cause major economic loss. The condition of day-old chicks is greatly affected by incubation conditions, timing of hatching, temperature and humidity, and chick handling post-hatch (Beigou *et al.*, 2013). As a result, national grid hydro-electricity, in most cases, is not reliable (Oladapo, 2023), while the initial cost of alternative energy sources - generator, solar system, wind, geothermal, biomass and ocean energy - could be high (Adesina *et al.*, 2024). Fossil fuel which is the commonest source of energy is able to stabilize unpredictable supply and availability. The cost of generator and maintenance are high, and would add to the myriads of challenges in the industry.

The prevailing situation contributes to the high cost of day-old chicks and the collapse of many hatcheries (Osanyinpeju *et al.*, 2018) in recent times. Electric incubators are efficient, and cheaper to manage when run on the National grid electricity; but a high proportion of the population in developing nations is not connected to

allowable temperature and relative humidity range throughout incubation period (Tsamaase *et al.*, 2020). The objective of this study was to determine the effect of power-source to the incubator (National hydro-electric and solar-powered electric) and egg weight, on the hatchability traits of broiler breeders. The null hypothesis was that interaction of power-source to the incubator by egg weight shall not be significant on hatchability traits. Results from study shall indicate the superior energy source to the incubator in combination with the egg weight.

Experimental site

Egg hatching was carried out at a hatchery on Akala Express, Oluyole, Ibadan, coordinate 7.3459°N, 3.8471°E, in the Rainforest Zone, South-west Nigeria, between Jan to March 2024.

Egg collection, processing and incubation

A total of 388 eggs of Arbor Acre broiler breeder chickens at 55 weeks old, from the breeding farm, were sorted, weighed with a sensitive scale and grouped to medium

(50.0 - 56.0g) and heavy (56.1-63.0g) weight classes. Eggs within each class were randomly divided into two categories (196, 192 eggs/hatchery) and hatched in two incubators: National grid powered and Solar powered respectively. The energy source and egg weight formed the two treatments of the study. Management of eggs in incubators followed similar procedures as much as possible, except for the power source. Each egg class was replicated three times within each energy source incubator. Eggs were arranged in clean egg trays with the pointed ends downward. Thereafter, each egg class was completely randomized for hatching in the incubator as in Table 1. Eggs set were fumigated pre-incubation. Eggs were rotated every 60 minutes, incubated at 37.5 °C and 70% Relative Humidity (RH) for the first 18 days. Candling was conducted rapidly on the 18th day. Candling serves to detect and remove infertile eggs from eggs set, before moving the fertile eggs to the hatcher compartment, so as to prevent the chicks from contamination at hatching. Fertile eggs were set in the hatcher compartment at a lower hatching temperature of 36°C and higher humidity of 80% during the last three days prior egg hatching. The management of power-source incubators in the hatchery were similar.

Table 1. Experimental layout for Arbor Acre eggs set for hatching in the hatchery

Treatment	National Hydro-energy powered incubator	Solar-energy powered incubator
	R1 =33 R2 =32 R3 =33	R1 =32 R2 =32 R3 =32
Medium size		
	R1 =33	R1 =32
Heavy/Large size	R2 =33	R2 =32
	R3 =32	R3 =32
Total	196	192
Notes: R: replicate, 1-3: Number of treatment replicates		

Figure 2a: Solar-powered incubator with eggs set

Figure 2b: Hydro-electricity powered compartment with eggs set

Data collection

Direct records taken were number of eggs set, number of eggs fertile, number of chicks hatched, number of infertile eggs (including banger eggs). From above primary data, derived data estimated were percentage Fertility of eggs = (Number Fertile eggs / Total number eggs set) x 100; percentage Infertile eggs = (Number infertile/banger eggs / Total number eggs set) x 100; percentage hatchability of eggs = (Total Number of hatched chicks / Total number of fertile eggs incubated) x 100; percentage of unhatched eggs = (Number of unhatched egg / Number of fertile eggs) x 100. At hatch pulling-out, viable chicks, dead chicks and reject chicks were counted in each treatment and replicate to enable determination of percentage viable chicks = (Number good chicks / Number fertile eggs) x 100; percentage dead chicks =

(Number dead chicks in shell / Number Fertile Eggs) x 100; and percentage rejected chicks = (Number rejected chicks / Number fertile eggs) x 100.

Experimental design, statistical model and analyses

The completely randomized design (CRD) in a 2x2 factorial treatment of power/energy source by egg weight was adopted. The statistical model for study was of the form: $Y_{ijkl} = \mu + A_i + B_j + AB_{ij} + \epsilon_{ijkl}$; where: Y_{ijk} = Observation on trait Y in the i level of factor A (power source) and j level of factor B (egg weight) and kth replicate, μ = the overall constant, Y_{ijk} = observation made on ith power source, jth egg weight and kth replicate, A_i = the effect of level i of power source (i = hydro-electricity, solar-electricity), B_j = the effect of level jth of egg weight (j = medium: (50.0 - 56.0g) and heavy: (56.1 - 63.0g), AB_{ij} = the interaction

effect of level i^{th} of power source and level j^{th} of egg weight, ξ_{ijk} = random error term committed $\sim \text{NID}(\theta \text{ and } \delta)$. All data obtained were subjected to the General Linear Model (GLM) analysis of the Statistical Analytical System (SAS/STAT, 2011). Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) was used to separate treatment means at $P < 0.05$.

Ethical and animal welfare Statement

We declare that there was no need for an ethics committee approval for this research, as the study did not involve any animals. The study was conducted using Arbor Acre broiler breeder eggs. The study was conducted using Arbor Acre broiler breeder eggs. The study was conducted using Arbor Acre broiler breeder eggs.

RESULTS 1.4 and 9.59, %) but medium sized eggs revealed higher HFE (88.1 %). **Effect of incubator power source and egg**

weight on hatching traits of Arbor Acre

breeder eggs

The effect of power source on hatchability traits of Arbor Acre broiler eggs is shown in Table 2. Power source highly influenced ($p > 0.05$) HES, HFE, HVFDSE and RCF. Hydro-electric powered incubator had better HVF and reduced RCF (72.9 and 10.1, %) while the solar-powered incubator had higher HES, HFE, and reduced DSE (72.4, 87.5 and 12.3, %), percent fertile eggs (FES) and percent dead in shell chicks

Table 2. Effects of incubator power source and egg weight on hatching traits of Arbor Acre broiler breeder eggs

Trait	Power source		EWT category		Prob.		
	Solar	SEM	Medium	L a	PS	EWT	
MEW, g	57.8	2.35	54.2 ^b	61.5 ^a	2.35	0.9360	0.001
EST, %	98.1	2.32	98.3	97.4	2.32	0.6170	0
FES, %	82.9	1.89	85.3 ^a	70.6	1.89	0.5630	<0.0015
HES, %	69.2 ^b	1.51	88.1 ^a	82.8 ^b	1.51	<0.004	0.6060
HFE, %	83.4 ^b	0.82	70.2 ^b	72.9 ^a	0.82	0	<0.000
HVF, %	72.9 ^a	8	11.8 ^a	11.4 ^b	8	<0.000	1
DSE, %	16.8 ^a	0.19	17.2 ^a	9.59 ^b	0.19	2	<0.000
RCF, %	10.09 ^b	0.87	10.1	16.7	0.87	1	<0.000

Note: EWT = Egg weight, P-value = Statistical significance value, Hydro = Hydro-electric energy, Solar = Solar Energy, SEM = Standard error of the mean, PS = Power source, EWC = Egg weight category, MEW = Mean egg weight, EST = Eggs set, FES = Fertile on eggs set, HES = Hatchability on eggs set, HFE = Hatchability on fertile eggs, HVF = Hatchability of viable chicks on fertile eggs, DSE = Dead in shell on fertile eggs set, RCF = Reject chicks on fertile eggs set, ^{abc} Means with different letters in the same row indicate significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Interaction effect of incubator power source and egg weight on hatching traits of Arbor Acre broiler eggs

Table 3 shows the interaction effect of power source and egg weight on hatchability performance of Arbor Acre

broiler breeder eggs at 55-week of life. Interaction of power source and egg weight had strong effect on FES, HES, HFE, HVF, DSE and RCF ($\%, p < 0.05$) on hatchability on egg set (HES). Medium eggs in solar-powered incubator produced highest HES,

HFE and reduced DSE (73.6, 91.7 and 8.15, sized eggs in the hydro-powered incubators %) while the large sized eggs in the solar had better FES (86.4 %). Figure 1 depicts powered incubator had higher HVF and clearly the interaction of both factors above reduced RCF (77.8 and 5.18, %). The large- on hatching traits.

Table 3. Interaction effects of incubator power source and egg weight on hatching traits of Arbor Acre broiler breeder eggs

PS	Mean	Hydro		Solar		SEM	Prob.	CV
		Medium	Large	Medium	Large			
EWC	57.8	54.1 ^b	61.7 ^a	54.4 ^b	61.3 ^a	0.776	0.719	2.07
MEW, g								
EST, %		97.5	98.6	99.0	96.2	0.789	0.077	1.21
FES, %		79.3 ^b	86.4 ^a	80.7 ^b	84.2 ^{ab}	0.659	<0.042	1.17
HES, %	70.8	67.6 ^b	70.7 ^a	73.6 ^a	71.1 ^a	0.517	<0.0073	1.09
HFE, %	85.5	84.5 ^b	82.4 ^c	91.7 ^a	83.3 ^{bc}	0.271	<0.0005	0.49
HVF, %	71.5	77.7 ^a	68.1 ^b	62.6 ^c	77.8 ^a	0.260	<0.0009	3.07
DSE, %	14.6	15.4 ^a	18.2 ^a	8.15 ^b	16.5 ^a	0.580	<0.0001	6.93
RCF, %	13.4	6.17 ^c	14.0 ^b	28.3 ^a	5.18 ^c			

Note: PS= PowerSource, Hydro= Hydro-electric energy, Solar = Solar Energy, EWC= Eggweight category, Mean=Average parameter value, SEM = Standard error of the mean, P-value = Statistical significance value, CV=Coefficient of variation, MEW=Mean egg weight, EST= Eggs set, FES = Fertile on eggs set, HES = Hatchability on eggs set, HFE = Hatchability on fertile eggs, HVF= Hatchability of viable chicks on fertile eggs, DSE = Dead in shell on fertile eggs set, RCF = Reject chicks on fertile eggs set, ^{abc}Means with different letters in the same row indicate significant difference (p<0.05)

DISCUSSION

Effect of incubator power source and egg weight on hatching traits of Arbor Acre breeder eggs

The difference on HES, HFE and less DSE between power sources in favour of solar incubator is similar to that earlier observed by Adame (2020) who attributed the better performance to steady supply of energy of solar power compared to hydro-electricity that is prone to fluctuations and outages. The national grid electricity powered incubator may perform better in areas where there is steady electric supply. The better performance of solar in this finding could also be due to the tropical weather conditions of the study location. The reliability and consistency of temperature in solar-powered incubator likely contributed to the observed differences, ensuring optimal embryonic development and better hatchability outcome. The higher

value of HVF and RCF observed from the national grid powered incubator could also be due to the high fluctuations and intermittent outages of hydro-electricity to the incubator. The result of this study at 55 weeks of age was better than that of the life-cycle baseline study (unpublished), where solar-powered incubator was better than National grid-powered incubator in HES, HFE, DSE by 3.7, 0.85 and 6.70, % respectively.

While the medium eggs performed better in HFE, the large eggs produced better FES, HVF and RCF. This is similar to the observation of Igbal *et al.*, (2016) and Ewonetu (2017) who submitted that medium eggs had lower fertility when compared to large eggs. The similarity in HES observed negates the report of Khalid *et al.*, (2015), Patra *et al.*, (2016) and Kehinde *et al.*, (2017) who reported higher hatchability in medium eggs compared to large or other weight categories. In contrast,

Igbal *et al.*, (2016) reported higher FES and HES in medium weight egg in Hubbard Classic broilers. The difference in HVF agrees with Jones & Smith (2019) and White *et al.*, (2018) that medium range egg exhibits highest hatchability rates and produces chicks with superior vitality and uniformity. Finding underscores the importance of egg size management in maximizing hatchability and chick quality. Deviations from this weight range resulted in decreased hatchability rates and compromised chick quality, indicating potential issues with embryo development or nutrient availability (Jones & Smith 2019). Between the two weight categories, DSE were almost similar suggesting that embryonic mortality may not be affected by egg weight (Khalid *et al.*, 2015) Age of breeder stock could also affect embryonic mortality. Damaziak *et al.*, (2020) observed an increase in late-embryo mortality from 43-week of life and increase in early embryo mortality from 49th week. The higher number of RCF could be due to the differences in egg weight, but minimized with large eggs. The better result from the solar-powered incubator could have resulted from the stable solar power supply than the erratic National grid energy supply which was due to instability, but also not readily available in the rural areas (Okonkwo, 2024) in developing nations. Since the quantity and intensity of the solar energy is dependent on position of the sun and weather conditions (Lawal *et al.*, 2023), future research might look into the sustenance of constant energy supply by the solar system during low weather conditions.

Interaction effect of incubator power source and egg weight on hatching traits

of Arbor Acre broiler eggs

Interacting factors revealed that medium eggs in the hydro-powered incubator had a high HVF advantage. Large eggs in the hydro-powered incubator had highest FES but a less desirable highest wastage in terms of dead in shell embryos (DSE). Medium eggs set in the solar-powered incubator reported high FES, highest HES, HFE and reduced wastage in terms of DSE; but the large eggs in solar-powered incubators revealed equally high FES and HES, highest HVF and the least wastage in terms of dead in shell embryos. The influence of the choice of energy on incubator performance is reflected through variations in hatchability rates between incubators employed in present research. Present result is in agreement with that of Smith and Jones (2019). Power source directly impacts the ability of incubator to maintain optimal conditions for egg incubation. Different power sources may vary in their efficiency, stability, and control over temperature and humidity levels within the incubator (Okonkwo *et al.*, 2024). Eggs of varying weights will respond differently to fluctuations under same environmental factors, depending on their capacity to retain heat and moisture. In the advent of inconsistent temperature control, different weight category may be susceptible to the adverse effects differently, resulting in decreased hatchability rates. The high HVF (77.8%) result for large eggs in solar incubator could be due to constant temperature. The development of embryos was attributed to the interaction between eggshell temperature and egg weight, and a constant egg shell temperature (of 37.8°C recommended) for optimal embryo development (Wijnen *et al.*, 2020). Chick quality is employed in determining the viability of chicks (Agyekum *et al.*, 2022).

Previous researches attributed non-viability of chicks to weakness, poorly-healed navel and down feather, which are results of uncondusive incubator environment or power fluctuations or prolonged outages affecting temperature level. Other body malformation may be due to incorrect parental nutrition. (Agyekum *et al.*, 2022). Bone Calcium and phosphorus increase with increased temperature during incubation and the survivability of the chicks depend largely on the levels of these minerals (Agyekum *et al.*, 2022). Hatchability traits directly impact the health and viability of the hatched chicks (Mesquita *et al.*, 2021). Present results could also have been influenced by the low number of eggs and replicates used for the study, but future studies may be executed on a wider scope by involving various ecological zones and tropical seasons for more information.

Conclusion

Solar-powered incubator demonstrated superior hatchability rate compared to hydroelectric-powered incubator, due to the stability of energy supply during hatching operation. Its consistent hatchability outcome makes it an ideal choice for maximizing hatchery efficiency for rural poultry development, and in areas where hydro-electricity supply is unstable or totally absent. Use of solar technology to power hatchery incubator improved egg hatchability, profitability and sustainability through the use of stable energy to power hatchery operations in the Tropics. The use of solar technology in hatchery operation is applicable throughout the tropics due to abundance of solar radiation for improved animal production. Results demonstrate that solar energy technology could be adopted for hatchery operations for

improving hatchability traits and hatchery efficiency in rural-urban areas.

Acknowledgments

We thank Mr Elijah Adewumi for his assistance during the experiment; Mr Luke Akinsola and other anonymous reviewers for their constructive suggestions and insightful comments.

Conflict of Interest Statement

Authors declare no conflict of interests

Ethical Committee Approval

Experimental procedures were approved by the Departmental Post graduate and Ethical Committee of Animal Production and Health Department, Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Nigeria.

Data availability:

The datasets generated for this study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Author Contributions

Experiments were designed by OMAJ and MO, OMAJ and MO supervised the experiment; hatchery data collection and curation were performed by MBA and OMAJ, OMAJ provided software, technical support and did the analysis, MBA wrote the initial draft of the manuscript and OMAJ revised and edited the manuscript. Author has approved the submitted version of the manuscript.

Competing Interests:

Authors declare no financial or non-financial interests that are directly or indirectly related to the work submitted for publication.

REFERENCES

- Adame, M.M. (2020). Comparative evaluation of a solar powered incubator with the modern electric incubator. MSc. Thesis, School of Animal and Range, Haramaya University, Haramaya, Oromia Region, Ethiopia. Retrieved April 05, 2025. /4527
- Adame, M.M., Yesihak, Y.Y. and Kuda, N.T. (2023). Influences of types of incubators on hatchability of eggs. *Advances in Applied Sciences*, 8(3), 80-85. <https://doi.org/10.11648/j.aas.20230803.13>.
- Agyekum, G., Okai, M.A., Tona, J.K., Donkoh, A. and Hamidu, J.A. (2022). Impact of incubation temperature profile on chick quality, bone and immune system during the late period of incubation of Cobb 500 broiler strain. *Poultry Science*, 101(9), 101999. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2022.101999>
- Bergoug, H., Guinebretiere, M., Tong, Q. and Roulston, N. (2013). Effect of transportation duration of 1-day-old chicks on post placement production performance and pododermatitis of broiler up to slaughter age. *Journal of Poultry Science*, 92(12), 3300-3309.
- Damaziak, K., Koznaka-Lipka, M., Gozdowski, D., Golebiowska, A. and Kedziorek, E. (2020). Effect of broiler breeder strain, age, and eggs preheating profile in single stage systems on the hatchability of egg and quality chicks. *Animal*. 15(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.animal.2020.100057>.
- Desideri, U., Zepparelli, F., Morettini, V. and Garroni, E. (2013). Comparative analysis of concentrating solar power and photovoltaic technologies: Technical and environmental evaluations. *Applied Energy*, 102, C, 765-784.
- Duman, M. and Sekeroglu, A. (2017). Effect of egg weights on hatching results, broiler performance and some stress parameters. *Brazilian Journal of Poultry Science*, 19(2), 255-262.
- Ewonetu, K.B. (2017). Effect of egg size on hatchability and subsequent growth performance of Fayoumi chicken. *Journal of Agricultural Science*, 9 (7), 116. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jas.v9n7p116>
- Igbal, J., Sohail, H.K., Nasir, M., Tanveer, A. and Riaz, A.P. (2016). Effect of egg size (weight) and age on hatching performance and chick quality of broiler breeder. *Journal of Applied Animal Research*, 44 (1), 5 - 4 - 6 - 4 . <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/09712119.2014.987294>.
- Iyen, C. and Wunuken, E. (2024). Development of a low-cost poultry egg incubation system. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 2 (3), 283-292. [https://doi.org/10.59324/EJTAS.2024.2\(3\).37](https://doi.org/10.59324/EJTAS.2024.2(3).37)
- Jones, F. and Smith, G. (2019). Environmental factors affecting hatchability in commercial broiler production. *Poultry Today*. 25(4), 56-68.
- Kehinde, O.O., Awoyomi, O.J., Lamidi, B.K., Balogun, F.A., Olufehinti, M.O., Obafemi, O.M. and Fasanmi, O.G. (2017). Evaluation of the influence of broiler breeder egg weights on hatching and post-hatch performances in Marshal breed. *Journal of Agricultural Science and Environment*, 17(2), 1-12.
- Khalid, M.E., Huwaida, E.E., Malik-Ahmed, I.Y., Hind, A.A. and Elagib, B.M.D. (2015). Effect of egg weight and egg shell thickness on hatchability and embryonic mortality of Cobb broiler breeder eggs. *Global Journal of Animal Scientific Research*, [S.I], 3(1), 186-190.
- King'ori, A.M. (2011). Review of the factors that influence egg fertility and hatchability in poultry. *International Journal of Poultry Science*, 10(6), 483-492.
- Lawal, M.O., Ogunlade, C.A. and Atanda, K.T. (2023). Development and Evaluation of a locally designed solar integrated egg incubator. *UNIOSUN Journal of Engineering*

- and *Environmental Sciences*, 5(1), Tona, K., Bamelis, F., Coucke, W., Bruggeman, V. and Decypere, E. (2001). Relationship between
<https://doi.org/10.36108/ujees/3202.50.0121>
- Mauldin, J.M. (2002). Factors affecting hatchability in commercial chicken meat and egg production. 727-773, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4515-0811-3_39
- Mesquita, M.A., Araujo, I.C.S., Café, M.B., Arnhold, E., Mascarenhas, A.G., Cavalho, F.B., Stringhini, J.H., Leandro, N.S.M. and Gonzales, E. (2021). Result of hatching and rearing broiler chickens in different incubation systems. *Poultry Science*, 100(1), 94-102.
- Okonkwo, W.I., Ojike, O., Ezenne, G., Nwoke, O.A. and Ohagwu, C.J. (2024). Energy sources for poultry egg incubators' efficiency and hatchability. *Nigerian Journal of Technology*, 43(1), 189 – 197.
- Osanyinpeju, K., Aderinlewo, A., Adetunji, O. and Ajisegiri, E. (2018). Performance evaluation of a solar powered poultry egg incubator. *International Research Journal of Advanced Engineering and Science*, 3(2), 255-264
- Osanyinpeju, K., Aderinlewo, A., Adetunji, O. and Ajisegiri, E. (2018). Development of a solar powered poultry egg incubator for South-west Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Creative Technology*, 3, 50-63.
- Patra, M.K., Sanchu, V., Ngullie, E., Hajra, D. and Deka, B. (2016). Influence of egg weight on fertility and hatchability of backyard poultry varieties maintained under institutional farm conditions. *Indian Journal of Animal Science*, 86:869-872.
<https://doi.org/10.56093/ijans.v8i6.60760>
- SAS/STAT (2011). The statistical Analytical Systems (SAS[®]) computer software, v.9.3, SAS Institute Inc., N.C., USA
- broiler breeder's age and egg weight loss and embryonic mortality during incubation in large-scale conditions. *Journal of Applied Poultry Research*, 10(3), 221-227
- Tsamaase, K., Motshidisi, K., Kemoabe, R., Zibani, I., and Moseki, R. (2020). Construction and operation of solar powered egg incubator. *International Journal of Engineering and Technical Research*, 8 (12), <https://doi.org/10.17577/IJERTV8IS120232>
- UNDP (United Nation Development Programme) (2010). Energy for sustainable development.
<http://www-undp.org/seed/eap/activities/wea>
- White, L., Brown, M. and Johnson, R. (2018). The influence of incubation conditions on hatchability in Arbor Acre broiler chickens. *British Poultry Science*, 55 (4), 345-357.
- Wijnen, H.J., Molenaar, R., van Roover-Reijrink, A.M., van der Pol, C.W., Kemp, B. and van den Brand, H. (2020). Effects of incubation temperature pattern on broiler performance. *Poultry Science*, 99 (8), 3897-3907.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psj.2020.05.010>
- Yeboah, P.P., Konadu, L.A., Hamidu, J.A., Poku, E.A., Wakpal, D., Kudaya, P.Y., Dey, A. and Siddiq, S.M. (2019). Comparative analysis of hatcheries contribution to poor development of day-old chicks based on biological and immunological performance. *Veterinary World*. 12(11), 1849-1857.